

Synthesis of Nitrophenacyl Bromides

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Phenacyl bromide and its substituted analogues have been used for the synthesis of 2,5-diphenylpyrazines (Staedel and Rugheimer, *Ber.*, 1876, 9, 563; Wolff, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 432; Gabriel, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1131; Tutin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 97, 2500; Ochai *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1939, 59, 462) and aroylbenzofurans (Rap, *Gazzetta*, 1895, 25, 285; Sen and Saxena, *this Journal*, 1958, 35, 136; 1959, 36, 283).

In connection with the preparation of some nitro derivatives of pyrazines and aroylbenzofurans, required for some investigations, a few nitrophenacyl bromides, namely, 3-nitro-4-chloro-, 3-nitro-4-bromo-, 3-nitro-4-methyl-, 2,4-dichloro-5-nitro- and 3,4-dichloro-5-nitro-phenacyl bromides have been obtained. When acidified ethanolic solution of potassium iodide is allowed to react and warmed, iodine is set free. On titrating against a standard sodium thiosulphate solution, it has been found that in all cases liberation of iodine is nearly quantitative and original acetophenone is obtained (cf. Garg *et al.*, *Agra Univ. J. Res.*, 1957, 6, 19; *this Journal*, 1957, 34, 286).

4-Chloro-, 4-bromo-, and 4-methyl- acetophenones were obtained by Friedel-Crafts' acetylation of the corresponding substituted benzenes. 2,4-Dichloro- and 3,4-dichloro-acetophenones were synthesised from the respective dichlorobenzenes, following the method described by Sodhan, Kshatriya, and Nargund (*this Journal*, 1947, 24, 373). 3-Nitro-4-chloro- (Le Fevre and Le Fevre, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1991; Kenford and Simpson, *ibid.*, 1947, 227), 3-nitro-4-bromo- (Ganguly and Le Fevre, *ibid.*, 1934, 852), 3-nitro-4-methyl- (Errera, *Gazzetta*, 1891, 21, 92), 3,4-dichloro-5-nitro- (Roberts and Tuner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1832), 2,4-dichloro-5-nitro- (Sacha and Patel, *this Journal*, 1957, 34, 821) acetophenones were prepared by nitration of the corresponding acetophenones.

3-Nitro-4-chlorophenacyl Bromide.—3-Nitro-4-chloroacetophenone (0.5M), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (300 g.), was warmed and treated with bromine (0.5M) dropwise. Acetic acid was distilled off and the phenacyl bromide was purified by recrystallisation from ethanol. Its characteristics and analytical data are shown in Table I.

By adopting this method, different colorless phenacyl bromides were prepared; their characteristics are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Phenacyl bromide.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Halogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	3-Nitro-4-chloro-	81%	84°	C ₈ H ₇ O ₂ NBrCl	41.30	41.37
2.	3-Nitro-4-bromo-	78	94°	C ₈ H ₇ O ₂ NBr ₂	49.21	49.53
3.	3-Nitro-4-methyl-	81	58°	C ₉ H ₉ O ₂ NBr	30.92	31.00
4.	2,4-Dichloro-5-nitro-	74	76°	C ₈ H ₄ O ₂ NBrCl ₂	47.88	48.24
5.	3,4-Dichloro-5-nitro-	78	138°	C ₈ H ₄ O ₂ NBrCl ₂	47.98	48.24

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